

Human-Robot Collaboration in progress!

Dear reader,

The #AIPRISM25 team welcomes you to this newsletter #3 which summarizes the last few months of our performance on the European stage of Human-Robot Collaboration.

As part of this journey, you have access to this compilation of activities, events and articles that we have prepared in the process of AI-powering human-centred robot interactions.

Enjoy your reading!

**Watch the AI-PRISM performance during the
European Robotics Forum 2024**

General Assembly in Turin

General Assembly

30-31 January 2024

Turin, Italy

aiprism.eu

The General Assembly of the AI-PRISM Project in Turin was marked by a comprehensive exploration of both user and technical perspectives, showcasing the project's vision and objectives. The meeting delved into various work packages, featuring insights from industrial scenarios to technical foundations, and even a guided tour of COMAU facilities.

[Find out more](#)

Tech Advancements

Demonstration as a key to evaluation

AI-PRISM

AI-PRISM kicks off the
system **demonstration** and
validation work

The AI-PRISM team has been working on developing a human-centred ecosystem of AI-based solutions for manufacturing scenarios for a year. Now, it is time to focus on real operational environments that will be used for **demonstrations to evaluate these solutions' performance**, transferability, scalability, and large-scale deployment. To achieve this, the team will conduct four pilot programs in key manufacturing sectors, including furniture, beverages, built-in appliances, electronics, and one generic demonstration facility.

The AI-PRISM consortium is dedicated to enhancing the EU Smart manufacturing value chain in four areas: collaborative environment, robot perception and recognition, robot programming, and human factors. Our industrial partners cooperate to achieve a balance between complementarity and overlap.

5 process innovations for human-centred AI-based solutions

Human-centred AI-based solutions for smart manufacturing

The AI-PRISM project will result in specific innovations for introducing cobots in manufacturing processes:

- Collaborative robotics in smart manufacturing
- AI Tools to enhance perception, reasoning and control capabilities in cobots
- Robot programming without highly skilled personnel – programming by demonstration
- Social sciences and humanities applied to collaborative robotic
- Positioning of AI-PRISM

Check them out

Researching and creating knowledge Check out our publications

AI-POWERED HUMAN-CENTRED ROBOT INTERACTIONS: CHALLENGES IN HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION ACROSS DIVERSE INDUSTRIAL SCENARIOS

Summary

The paper describes the AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions (AI-PRISM) project, focusing on enhancing human-robot collaboration (HRC) in various industrial scenarios to improve productivity and worker well-being. AI-PRISM aims to simplify HRC for SMEs, developing human-centered AI enhanced collaborative robotics applications.

The paper outlines key challenges like safety, seamless communication and balancing automation with human skill, through the five user pillars in different sectors. Leveraging AI to enhance robotic perception, reasoning, and coordination, AI-PRISM seeks to make industrial processes more efficient, flexible, and less stressful for human workers.

Highlights

AI-PRISM prioritizes human-centred challenges like worker well-being through advanced robotics that understand and adapt to human needs and work environments. It demonstrates potential benefits across multiple sectors by integrating AI-driven robots into the workforce, supporting significant advancements in industrial automation and human-robot synergy. The paper includes emerging AI to improve data communication and efficiency in human-robot interactions, aiming for user-friendly programming for SMEs, and following a human-centric approach to robotics.

Authors

Francisco Javier Gonzalez-Pedreira (Co-Chair)
Sergio Torralba (Moderator/President)

EUROPEAN ROBOTICS FORUM
Member of the Forum

MARCH 13-15 2024

alprism.eu

AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions: Challenges in Human-Robot Collaboration Across Diverse Industrial Scenarios

The paper describes the AI-Powered Human-Centred Robot Interactions (AI-PRISM) project, focusing on enhancing human-robot collaboration (HRC) in various industrial scenarios to improve productivity and worker well-being. AI-PRISM aims to simplify HRC for SMEs, developing human-centered AI enhanced collaborative robotics applications.

Towards More Effective Human-Robot Collaboration via Accurate Pose Estimation

This paper explores the pivotal role of accurate pose estimation in enhancing Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) effectiveness, focusing on the integration of AI-based zero-shot estimation algorithms within collaborative robotic platforms for industrial scenarios.

AI-PRISM

TOWARDS MORE EFFECTIVE HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION VIA ACCURATE POSE ESTIMATION

Summary

This paper explores the pivotal role of accurate pose estimation in enhancing Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) effectiveness, focusing on the integration of AI-based zero-shot estimation algorithms within collaborative robotic platforms for industrial scenarios.

Object 6D pose estimation is crucial in HRC as it enables robots to perceive the collaborative environment and react accordingly to human actions. Zero-shot object 6D pose estimation models offer safety and flexibility in dynamic manufacturing environments without previous training, but their integration presents challenges in sensor, model deployment, and seamless robot control integration.

Highlights

The article provides insights into the advancements, challenges and practical applications of AI-based zero-shot pose estimation techniques in enhancing Human-Robot Collaboration within industrial scenarios. It highlights the integration of traditional deep learning methods for pose estimation, which often rely on supervised learning paradigms requiring extensive labeled training data. To address these limitations, zero-shot learning strategies aim to enhance model generalization and reduce reliance on extensive training data. It is presented through an example application that illustrates the architecture designed for HRC applications.

Authors

Francisco Javier Gonzalez-Pedreira (Co-Chair)
Sergio Torralba (Moderator/President)

EUROPEAN ROBOTICS FORUM
Member of the Forum

MARCH 13-15 2024

alprism.eu

AI-PRISM

ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT FOR HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION IN A FURNITURE PAINTING CELL

Summary

Advances in robotics can create safe, dynamic, and real-time decision-making automated solutions for collaborative working environments between humans and robots. This paper presents a human-robot collaboration system for a furniture painting cell. The aim is to increase the level of automatization of the painting process and minimize the repetitive operations performed in the conventional manual painting process.

The use of autonomous robot arms, programmed by demonstration, reduces the operator's exposure time to chemicals involved in the painting process and minimizes the repetitive movements performed during manual painting, which will improve human safety. Current research aims to define a framework where humans and robots can share the working area simultaneously thanks to integrating several systems to control the working environment, the robot arm, and the operator, addressing human-centred challenges to achieve a symbiotic, collaborative painting cell.

Highlights

The framework aims to reduce the cycle time, labor and costs compared with manual painting operations. The outstanding feature of the solution is real-time sensor integration to achieve reactive control and error operations, real-time control programming by demonstration, and task scheduling to achieve a balanced workload for human operators. Thanks to this, the operator shifts from the execution of repetitive tasks to a supervisory role of watching the robot and rejecting the quality of the process.

Authors

Juan Luis Gonzalez-Pedreira (Co-Chair)
Francisco Javier Gonzalez-Pedreira (Co-Chair)
Sergio Torralba (Moderator/President)

EUROPEAN ROBOTICS FORUM
Member of the Forum

MARCH 13-15 2024

alprism.eu

On the development of programming by demonstration environment for Human-Robot Collaboration in a furniture painting cell

Advances in robotics can create safe, dynamic, and real-time decision-making automated solutions for collaborative working environments between humans and robots. This paper presents a human-robot collaboration system for a furniture painting cell. The aim is to increase the level of automatization of the painting process and minimize the repetitive operations performed in the conventional manual painting process.

A Concise Taxonomy of Human-Robot Interactions and Soft Skills Synergy

With the substantial interest in human-centered manufacturing, human interactions with robots and embodied Artificial Intelligence (AI) have become more significant. Major topics related to the Human-Robot Interactions (HRI) include the mode of the interaction and the aspect of interaction.

[Read more about publications](#)

Women's Day Campaign

In parallel to the technical advancements of the project, we have been active in raising awareness campaigns for topics that are of relevant concern, coinciding with international days and other initiatives. This time we're thrilled to announce that the AI-PRISM Consortium Partners are joining the #InspireInclusion International Campaign in honor of Women's Day!

Bianca Muntean
PhD
Transilvania IT

We are sharing the quote from Bianca Muntean, PhD from Transilvania IT Cluster on her approach to challenges facing women worldwide in terms of inclusion: "As someone deeply involved in the tech world and a woman who has navigated her way to leadership positions, I see firsthand the challenges women face worldwide when it comes to inclusion. One of the most significant hurdles is ensuring equal access to education and skills development, particularly in the tech field."

[Learn more](#)

Beatriz Andrés Navarro,
Associate Professor
Universitat Politècnica de València

Laura Moya Ruiz
R&D Engineer
Universitat Politècnica de València

In the 2nd post taking part in the International #InspireInclusion Womens' Day we were presenting the quote from Beatriz Andrés Navarro, Associate Professor from Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)

[Learn more](#)

In the 3rd post taking part in the International #InspireInclusion Womens' Day we were presenting the quote from Laura Moya Ruiz, R&D Engineer from Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)

[Learn more](#)

Events

ERF Conference 2024

The European Robotics Forum 2024 held in Rimini, Italy, proved to be an exceptional platform for showcasing the groundbreaking contributions of AI-PRISM. Amidst a backdrop of innovation and collaboration, AI-PRISM made significant strides, leaving a lasting impression on attendees and industry experts alike. In April, the AI-PRISM team took part in the Digital Manufacturing Industrial Summit in Valencia, Spain. We organised the "Robotics in Manufacturing" workshop and participated in the "Manufacturing Reconfiguration and Flexibility" workshop along with other European projects.

[Learn more](#)

I-ESA Conference 2024

In the scenic backdrop of Chania, Crete, Greece, the I-ESA Conference 2024 witnessed a workshop under the auspices of the AI-PRISM project. Titled 'Enhancing Enterprise Interoperability through Human-Centered Collaborative Robotics: Best Practices and Standards,' the workshop aimed to delve into the intersection of human-centric collaborative robotics (HRC), data, artificial intelligence (AI), and social sustainability. Spearheaded by Francisco Fraile, the workshop's agenda promised a comprehensive exploration of challenges, presentations on innovative solutions, and insightful discussions revolving around HRC interoperability.

[Learn more](#)

STAY TUNED TO THE AI-PRISM SMART JOURNEY 🚀

[AI-PRISM Horizon Europe](#)

This email was sent to {{contact.EMAIL}}

You've received it because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

This newsletter has been prepared by the [AI-PRISM project](#). It does not reflect the opinion of any single AI-PRISM partner. The [AI-PRISM project](#) and its consortium partners are not liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of this publication.

[View in browser](#) | [Unsubscribe](#)

